

IPT alumni spotlight

MEET SUZANNE

Suzanne Zamany Andersen represented **Denmark** at the IPT 2014 and IPT 2015, and was a juror and a team leader at the IPT 2018, IPT 2019 and IPT 2022.

Looking back, what first motivated you to join the International Physicists' Tournament?

Honestly, as a student, it was the chance to travel. It seemed exciting to go visit other universities and hear about the experiences of other students in different universities. Secondary was the fun physics problems.

Which IPT problem or experience left the strongest impression on you – and why?

There's two that comes to mind, for very different reasons. The first and strongest one was the electrohydrodynamic lifter problem from 2015. I had a SUPER solution for that problem, and had just spent so many months on it, and was completely taken with the physics. We got in the finale, and I got to present and got us a second place that year, which is the best Denmark has ever performed in the tournament. It was just a really great problem, with the perfect combination of experiments and theory (which almost matched! Who knew that could happen?). I also had a few judges who came up to me after that problem and said they would have ranked it higher, which really boosted my confidence as a young student.

Secondly, was an acoustic train problem from 2014 that I had also worked on, which was interesting physics, got me into a sound proof room, and I spent a lot of time recording trains. But what stood out to me was that I was the reporter, Sweden the Opponent, and Ukraine the Reviewer. And the whole session was just really positive. We were all coming up with ideas together, and brainstorming on the stage how to improve the problem and way to measure. And we all scored high, because the judges liked the collaborative nature of the discussion. I have almost never seen another physics fight that was as positive in the 6 years I both did IPT and was a juror. Wish it was more common!

Team Denmark in the IPT 2014 finale

Where has your journey taken you since your IPT days academically?

I'm currently a CEO and start-up founder, so my job is basically everything. I currently manage a company of 18 people, I've pioneered a new field of electrochemistry, I successfully raised 3.5M EUR in equity funding from investors, and 2.8M in grants, I do customer management, stakeholder management, board management, PR, HR, legal, accounting, website: Chief Everything Officer as I call it. We're now building our first container-sized demo unit, which will be placed on a customer site next summer, and while this is happening, I'm gearing up for a fundraise of 10-15M EUR in 2026. For that, I'm frequently on stage, both in presentations about NitroVolt, and on panel discussions about bringing research from the university to the "real world". Being comfortable on stage is super important to my work. Problem solving when you have very little information is a great skill that IPT taught me. Leadership is another important skill I have developed for my work, and keep developing. I have to both lead myself, lead a team of 18 people, and lead change on a global plan. Each type of leadership is very different, and something I hope to always keep improving.

How did participating in the IPT shape your approach to research, teamwork, or communication in your later studies or career?

Tremendously! It exposed me to so many new avenues of physics and problem solving that wasn't covered in my studies. It made me better at organizing my approach to problems, and better at presenting and communicating results. It also supported me in developing better networking skills, as I was exposed to people from all over the world. I sincerely wish that more students had this opportunity, because it really was extraordinary.

Suzanne as a CEO of NitroVolt

What's one skill or lesson from the IPT that you still find yourself using today?

Ask for help. If you don't know something, find an expert, and ask for help to understand a problem.

